

Heat transfer at the interface during drop impact on a moving substrate

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(Received xx; revised xx; accepted xx)

The thermal interactions of liquid droplets impacting a moving substrate are investigated, combining theoretical modelling with experimental validation. An analytical model is developed to predict the time-evolving contact temperature and heat flux at the droplet–substrate interface. The model incorporates contact resistance, which is a critical parameter that was often neglected in earlier studies.

High-speed infrared thermography is used to measure transient temperature fields with high spatial and temporal resolution, providing experimental data to validate the theoretical predictions. The model is validated for different droplet diameters, substrate velocities, and thermal conditions. The findings demonstrate that substrate velocity and droplet diameter have negligible influence on the thermal behaviour within the tested parameter space. Furthermore, including contact resistance eliminates the initial heat flux singularities predicted by earlier models, providing a finite and physically realistic result.

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1. Introduction

Understanding droplet impact on solid surfaces is critical for various engineering applications, including spray cooling, coating technologies, and ice accretion in aeronautical systems. In particular, in icing conditions, droplet impact is the precursor to ice formation, making accurate heat transfer modelling essential for predicting ice growth. This study is motivated by the need to improve thermal modelling in such applications, where droplet impact dictates the initial thermal exchange at the interface. Given its significance in both fundamental research and practical applications, droplet impact has been extensively studied over the years. The interest in this phenomenon dates back nearly one and a half centuries to the pioneering observations of [Worthington \(1877\)](#). As noted by [Thoroddsen *et al.* \(2008\)](#), the advent of high-speed imaging techniques has greatly increased interest in this field, providing deeper insights over recent decades. This interest spans multiple fields and applications; for instance, the control and understanding of droplet impact dynamics have led to advancements in spray-based technologies, such as fuel injection in internal combustion engines, as reviewed by [Moreira *et al.* \(2010\)](#). In forensic science, impact patterns have been analysed to reconstruct events, as discussed by [Adam \(2012\)](#), [Brodbeck \(2012\)](#), and [Laan *et al.* \(2014\)](#). Surface engineering has also benefited from research on droplet interactions with complex substrates, as examined by [Marengo *et al.* \(2011\)](#). In applications related to icing, droplet impact serves as a precursor to ice formation, influencing aircraft safety and power infrastructure, as reviewed in [Roisman & Tropea \(2021\)](#). In the aerospace and renewable energy sectors, the ability to control droplet impact is crucial for minimising substrate damage. For instance, [Keegan *et al.* \(2013\)](#) studied the erosion of wind turbines, while [Zhang *et al.* \(2021\)](#) analysed the degradation of protective coatings. These diverse applications highlight the broad relevance of understanding droplet impact across multiple disciplines.

Dimensionless parameters governing the drop impact dynamics and the phenomena associated with drop spreading and splashing include the Reynolds Re and Weber We numbers, which are defined as:

$$Re_{d,i} = \frac{\rho_d D U_{d,i}}{\mu_d}, \quad We_{d,i} = \frac{\rho_d D U_{d,i}^2}{\sigma_d}, \quad (1.1)$$

where D and U are the drop initial diameter and impact velocity, μ_d , ρ_d , and σ_d denote the dynamic viscosity, density, and surface tension of the liquid drop, respectively. The subscript i distinguishes whether the parameter is based on the normal or tangential relative velocity component between the droplet and the substrate.

Over the decades, [Rein \(2002\)](#), [Yarin \(2006\)](#), [Josserand & Thoroddsen \(2016\)](#), and [Mohammad Karim \(2023\)](#) have provided comprehensive reviews summarising progress in understanding droplet impact. Early studies primarily focused on cases involving high Reynolds and Weber numbers with single droplets.

For example, [Yarin & Weiss \(1995\)](#) investigated periodic droplet trains impacting substrates and extended theoretical insights to single-droplet impacts on dry surfaces. Their approach introduced a self-similar solution for the internal flow during spreading, which laid the groundwork for subsequent investigations. Building on this foundation, [Roisman *et al.* \(2009\)](#) and [Roisman \(2009\)](#) refined self-similar solutions of the Navier–Stokes equations to predict the maximum spreading diameter and the residual film thickness under isothermal conditions. Subsequently, [Riboux & Gordillo \(2014\)](#) developed theories on the critical impact speed required for drop splashing, which they expanded in [Riboux & Gordillo \(2015\)](#) to quantify the mass and velocities of the ejected droplets. For asymmetric spreading, [García-Gejo *et al.* \(2020\)](#), drawing on the theoretical framework of [Gordillo *et al.* \(2019\)](#), predicted the time-evolving shape of the border of the thin liquid film. [Xu *et al.* \(2005\)](#) investigated how

the surrounding gas pressure affects the stresses and flow fields within the spreading droplet. Additionally, [Stow & Hadfield \(1981\)](#), [Range & Feuillebois \(1998\)](#), [Xu \(2007\)](#), [Latka *et al.* \(2012\)](#), [Quetzeri-Santiago *et al.* \(2019\)](#), and [García-Geijo *et al.* \(2021\)](#) studied the effects of substrate roughness, while [Bartolo *et al.* \(2005\)](#), [Quére \(2008\)](#) and [Antonini *et al.* \(2012\)](#) emphasised the critical role of wettability. Studies by [Antonini *et al.* \(2014\)](#), [Yeong *et al.* \(2014\)](#), [LeClerc *et al.* \(2016\)](#), [Regulagadda *et al.* \(2018\)](#), and [Aboud & Kietzig \(2018\)](#) also considered non-axisymmetric impacts and examined the performance of specialised substrates, such as superhydrophobic and icephobic materials, to enhance anti-icing solutions.

Substrate motion introduces an additional complexity, as investigated by [Mundo *et al.* \(1995\)](#), [Almohammadi & Amirfazli \(2017\)](#), and [Buksh *et al.* \(2019\)](#). Inclined-impact configurations can replicate certain aspects of a moving substrate at low velocities, as demonstrated by [Buksh *et al.* \(2020\)](#). However, [Povarov *et al.* \(1976\)](#) and [Stumpf *et al.* \(2024\)](#) reported that sufficiently high substrate speeds generate boundary layers strong enough to induce aerodynamic rebound, resulting in dynamics that do not occur in inclined-impact scenarios.

Although these investigations provided profound insights into isothermal conditions, incorporating thermal effects such as heating, cooling, or phase change is still challenging. For example, when the substrate is heated, [Senda *et al.* \(1988\)](#) and [Bernardin *et al.* \(1997\)](#) demonstrated that phenomena like the Leidenfrost effect can significantly alter flow patterns and breakup modes. Understanding these transitions is critical for applications such as spray cooling of hot surfaces, as emphasised by [Breitenbach *et al.* \(2018\)](#). Conversely, when a droplet solidifies upon impact, its morphology evolves differently. Such scenarios arise in processes including spray forming, as [Orme \(1993\)](#) described, plasma spray coating, studied by [Fauchais \(2004\)](#), thin-film fabrication, as noted by [Steirer *et al.* \(2009\)](#), and ice accretion in aeronautical applications, as discussed by [Cao *et al.* \(2018\)](#). Accurate characterisation of thermal behaviour at the droplet–substrate interface is essential for predicting and analysing droplet impact outcomes. [Tarozi *et al.* \(2007\)](#), [Teodori *et al.* \(2018\)](#), [Schmidt *et al.* \(2020\)](#), [Gholijani *et al.* \(2020\)](#), and [Gholijani *et al.* \(2022\)](#) demonstrated that infrared thermography is a highly effective technique for capturing rapidly changing temperature fields during impact. In this study, we utilise an infrared-transparent substrate with an appropriate coating to obtain detailed, two-dimensional temperature fields at high temporal resolution, enabling precise measurements of contact temperature distributions and heat fluxes.

Thermal modeling of drop impact has traditionally been based on simplified frameworks since the real problem is rather complicated. For instance, [Seki *et al.* \(1978\)](#) proposed for the description of the heat transfer in a droplet suddenly coming into contact with a solid wall to use a one-dimensional model for heat conduction in two semi-infinite solid regions ([Carslaw & Jaeger 1959](#)). The expressions for the contact temperature T_c and the heat flux at the interface q_c are obtained in the form

$$T_{c, \text{Seki}} = \frac{e_d T_d + e_w T_w}{e_d + e_w}, \quad q_{c, \text{Seki}} = \frac{e_d e_w (T_w - T_d)}{\sqrt{\pi t} (e_d + e_w)}. \quad (1.2)$$

Here, T_d and T_w represent the temperatures of the liquid and solid, respectively, while e_d and e_w denote their thermal effusivities.

This approach has been later generalized by accounting for the contact resistance ([Aziz & Chandra 2000](#)). Furthermore, the solution for the flow in a spreading drop ([Roisman 2009](#)) has been used in the theoretical solution [Roisman \(2010\)](#), which accounts for the convection terms

$$T_{c, \text{Roisman}} = \frac{e_d T_d + e_w \mathcal{F}(Pr_d, 0, \infty) T_w}{e_d + \mathcal{F}(Pr_d, 0, \infty) e_w}, \quad q_{c, \text{Roisman}} = \frac{e_d e_w (T_w - T_d)}{\sqrt{\pi t} (e_d + e_w \mathcal{F}(Pr_d, 0, \infty))} \quad (1.3)$$

Figure 1: Illustration of the experimental setup developed to investigate heat transfer during droplet impact. The setup comprises a droplet-generation system, a rotating sapphire disk as the substrate, high-speed cameras for visualising droplet dynamics, an infrared camera for capturing temperature fields, and environmental monitoring equipment.

The term \mathcal{F} in the right-hand side of equations (1.3) accounts for the influence of convective effects in the liquid phase and is a function of the liquid Prandtl number Pr_d , computed in Roisman (2010).

Although several studies have measured contact temperatures on stationary substrates, no corresponding data for moving substrates are available in the existing literature. The validity of the existing models requires an accurate experimental evaluation and validation.

This study has been primarily motivated by the need for improved heat transfer modelling in applications where liquid droplet impact plays a crucial role, such as ice accretion, where it acts as a precursor to the freezing process. Specifically, we examine how droplet diameter, substrate speed, and thermal boundary conditions influence contact temperatures and heat fluxes. Our theoretical approach builds on the solution obtained in Carslaw & Jaeger (1959), incorporating the convective effect related to the velocity of the spreading drop. These developments are complemented by high-resolution experiments using high-speed imaging and infrared thermography, providing a comprehensive understanding of the flow and thermal fields during the early stages of droplet impact on a moving substrate.

2. Experimental study

2.1. Experimental setup

An experimental setup was developed to investigate the heat transfer mechanisms during droplet impact. The configuration is schematically illustrated in figure 1. Droplets of double-distilled water are generated within a temperature-controlled cooling chamber (marked 4 in figure 1), ensuring consistent and well-defined initial and ambient conditions. The temperature of the droplets is measured using a type-T thermocouple, 5, with an accuracy of $\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$, positioned inside the droplet-generation needle. The cooling system, 3, ensures precise control of the droplet's initial temperature. The moving substrate consists of a graphite-coated sapphire disk, 8, that serves as the target surface. This substrate is rotated using a geared motor, 9, with precise speed control, allowing for accurate setting of the angular velocity. A magnetic encoder, 10, is used to provide feedback on the disk's rotation, which is managed by a motor driver controller, 11. To synchronise the measurements, a data acquisition system, 16, is used, while environmental parameters, such as humidity and temperature, are monitored using a dedicated sensor, 13, with data retrieved by a microcontroller, 14. The PC, 15, is used for data logging and processing. The impact radius, R , is fixed at 73 ± 1 mm, and, based on Pier (2013), no edge effects are present in the boundary layer. A high-speed camera 2, positioned laterally to the substrate, records the impact dynamics, enabling measurement of the droplet's normal velocity relative to the substrate, $U_{d,n}$, and its diameter, D . A high-speed infrared camera, 1, is positioned orthogonally to the substrate's axis of rotation to capture the thermal interactions during droplet impact.

Exemplary side-view images of the spreading drop are shown in figure 2. These were captured using the high-speed video system, 2. Thermocouple measurements are used to extract the corresponding temperature-dependent properties of water from VDI (2013).

In the laboratory reference frame, the droplet possesses no tangential velocity. Consequently, its tangential velocity relative to the substrate equals the substrate speed, $\omega R = U_{d,t}$, where ω is the angular velocity of the substrate, derived from the motor's rotational speed, n . The Reynolds number for the airflow induced by the moving substrate is denoted by $Re_s = \omega R^2 / \nu_a$, where ν_a is the kinematic viscosity of air. In these experiments, Re_s ranges from 2000 to 30,000. According to Kobayashi (1994), the critical Reynolds number for the onset of instabilities in the boundary layer, Re_{cr} , is 4.5×10^4 . As the maximum Re_s investigated remains below this threshold, the boundary layer surrounding the droplet remains laminar throughout the experimental conditions. Understanding the airflow is crucial, as a strongly turbulent boundary layer, as highlighted by Stumpf *et al.* (2024), can lead to droplet deformation and subsequent aerodynamic rebound.

The disk is composed of an infrared-transmissive material (aluminium oxide, Al_2O_3 , also known as sapphire). To ensure accurate infrared measurements, the impact surface of the disk is coated with a highly emissive graphite-based paint. The influence of this coating on the measurements is considered negligible, an assumption widely supported in the literature (Chaze *et al.* 2019; Gholijani *et al.* 2020; Schmidt *et al.* 2020). The estimated time required for the thermal boundary layer within the coating to develop fully is given by $t \propto \epsilon^2 / \alpha_c$, where ϵ denotes the thickness of the coating, and α_c is its thermal diffusivity. In these experiments, the average thickness of the coating is $8 \mu\text{m}$, and the thermal diffusivity is approximately $2 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. This yields an estimated development time of $t \approx 0.032$ ms, which is significantly shorter than the temporal resolution of $\Delta t = 0.15$ ms given by the infrared camera.

The infrared camera is positioned beneath the disk to capture transient temperature measurements during droplet impact. In the experiments, droplet temperature, diameter, and substrate speed are systematically varied. The substrate temperature, monitored with

Figure 2: Representative images of droplet impact on a moving substrate. Panels (a) and (b) show the droplet impact at a substrate velocity of 0.38 m/s, with a droplet diameter $D = 2.45$ mm, normal impact velocity $U_{d,n} = 3.13$ m/s, and initial droplet temperature $T_{d,0} = 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. Panels (c) and (d) depict the droplet impact at a substrate velocity of 6.12 m/s under otherwise identical conditions. An asymmetry in the droplet spreading is visible, arising from the increased substrate motion.

temperature sensors, varied with ambient room conditions and ranged from 24.1°C to 33.0°C across all experiments.

Table 1 summarises the experimental conditions tested in this study. A full factorial design was used to investigate the interactions between these parameters, with the droplet's normal impact velocity held constant.

2.2. Calibration of the infrared camera

The infrared camera is calibrated in situ using the setup illustrated in figure 3. A copper plate, cooled by a chiller, extends beyond the camera's entire field of view, ensuring uniform calibration across the measurement area.

Temperature images are not directly obtained from the infrared camera; instead, the digital level (DL) recorded by the camera is converted into temperature values. The calibration process involves incrementally increasing the temperature of a reference surface from 16°C to 35°C , with calibration images captured at 1°C intervals. The variation in DL is recorded as a function of the surface temperature (T), establishing a calibration curve. This relationship between DL and T is governed by Planck's law, which describes the spectral radiant emittance of an object as a function of its temperature:

Parameter	Tested Conditions	Maximum Uncertainty
D (mm)	1.53, 1.95, 2.45	± 0.03
$U_{d,t}$ (m/s)	0.38, 1.53, 3.06, 4.59, 6.11	± 0.17
$U_{d,n}$ (m/s)	3.13	± 0.15
$T_{d,0}$ ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	0.5, 10, 15	± 0.5
$Re_{d,n}$	2660 – 4406	± 425
$Re_{d,t}$	1566 – 13608	± 612
$We_{d,n}$	200 – 292	± 41
$We_{d,t}$	90 – 1169	± 88

Table 1: Summary of the experimental conditions tested in this study. A full factorial design was used to systematically vary droplet diameter (D), substrate speed ($U_{d,t}$), and droplet temperature ($T_{d,0}$). The droplet’s normal impact velocity ($U_{d,n}$) was held constant, while key non-dimensional parameters, including the normal and tangential Reynolds ($Re_{d,n}$, $Re_{d,t}$) and Weber numbers ($We_{d,n}$, $We_{d,t}$), were computed over the range of experimental conditions.

Figure 3: Schematic of the calibration setup for the infrared camera. The setup includes a temperature-controlled copper plate thermally coupled to the sapphire disk via a thin layer of thermal paste, ensuring uniform heat transfer. A thermocouple is embedded at the surface to monitor and maintain the substrate temperature accurately. The sapphire disk, coated with a high-emissivity material, serves as the substrate for infrared measurements. The field of view (FOV) of the infrared camera captures the temperature distribution at the coating bottom surface.

$$W_b(\lambda, T_{\text{obj}}) = \frac{2\pi hc^2}{\lambda^5} \frac{1}{\left(e^{\frac{hc}{\lambda k T_{\text{obj}}}} - 1 \right)},$$

where h is Planck’s constant, k is Boltzmann’s constant, c is the speed of light, λ is the wavelength, and T_{obj} is the temperature of the object.

Numerous studies, including those by [Martiny *et al.* \(1996\)](#), [Schulz \(2000\)](#), [Ochs *et al.* \(2009\)](#), [Elfner *et al.* \(2017\)](#), [Falsetti *et al.* \(2021\)](#), and [Sisti *et al.* \(2021\)](#), have based their infrared camera calibration on the above equation. By rearranging the terms and isolating T ,

the following semi-empirical relation is obtained:

$$T = \frac{r}{\ln\left(\frac{b}{I_{\text{obj}}} + f\right)},$$

where I_{obj} is the digital level recorded by the camera, and r , b , and f are calibration parameters. These parameters were estimated in situ using a thermocouple as the reference and a nonlinear least-squares fitting procedure applied to the calibration images obtained with the setup illustrated in figure 3.

From the calibration process, two types of errors are quantified: the temporal noise in the temperature readings and the corresponding noise-equivalent heat flux. The temporal noise, σ_T , is defined as:

$$\sigma_T = \frac{1}{N_{\text{pixels}}} \sum_{j=1}^{N_{\text{pixels}}} \sigma_{T,j}, \quad (2.1)$$

where $\sigma_{T,j}$ represents the standard deviation of temperature fluctuations for pixel j across multiple frames i , given by:

$$\sigma_{T,j} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N_{\text{frames}}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{\text{frames}}} (T_{i,j} - \bar{T}_j)^2}. \quad (2.2)$$

Here, N_{pixels} is the total number of pixels in the region of interest, and N_{frames} is the number of frames captured during the calibration measurement. $T_{i,j}$ denotes the temperature of pixel j in frame i , and \bar{T}_j is the average temperature of pixel j across all frames. The overall temperature noise, σ_T , is computed as the average of $\sigma_{T,j}$ over all pixels within the region of interest.

The calculated temporal noise, σ_T , is 0.21°C . This value quantifies the variation in temperature readings over time. The corresponding noise-equivalent heat flux is determined separately through numerical simulation of the transient Fourier heat equation applied to the substrate. By analysing the artificial heat flux generated by temperature fluctuations between consecutive frames, the heat flux noise is estimated to be 10^4 W/m^2 . Further details on the heat flux calculations are provided in section § 2.4.

2.3. Temperature measurements

The experimental contact temperature values were directly obtained from the infrared camera measurements. A time-lapse sequence of the thermal evolution during droplet impact is shown in figure 4. The colder region represents the area wetted by the droplet, delineated by a sharp temperature gradient in the vicinity of the three-phase contact line. The contact area between the droplet and the substrate increases over time. Figures 4a to 4d correspond to four successive time steps: 0.57 ms, 1.03 ms, 1.61 ms, and 2.07 ms after impact. As time progresses, the expansion of the contact area results from both droplet spreading and entrainment due to the relative motion with the substrate. To determine a single representative value for the contact temperature, T_c , the average temperature over the droplet–surface contact area was used. This approach is justified by the uniformity of the temperature across the contact region, as evident in figure 4. A slight deviation, specifically a lower temperature difference of approximately $0.2 - 0.3^\circ\text{C}$, is observed in the initial contact area of the droplet, as evidenced in figure 4d. This phenomenon can be attributed to the influence of the droplet's initial normal velocity, which reduces the contact resistance (Aziz & Chandra 2000) and consequently results in a slightly lower contact temperature in this region.

The contact temperature evolutions derived from experiments are given as a function of

Figure 4: Time-lapse sequence showing the thermal evolution during the impact of a droplet on a moving substrate, recorded using an infrared camera. The droplet, with a diameter of 1.95 mm and an initial temperature of 0.5°C, impacts a substrate rotating at 800 r.p.m. Snapshots are taken at different times following impact: 0.57 ms, 1.03 ms, 1.61 ms, and 2.07 ms. The temperature distribution within the droplet-substrate contact region remains mostly uniform, with slight deviations observed at the leading edge during initial contact.

time for four different substrate velocities in Figs. 5a-d. In addition to the experimental values and their associated error, comparisons are made with existing models (1.2) and (1.3) from the literature. These models predict a constant contact temperature, marked in figure 5 by dashed lines. Both theories underpredict temperatures. In this study, an improved model has been proposed, which accounts for convective effects and thermal resistance at the interface. Exemplary results of this model are plotted as blue curves in Figs. 5a-d. The theoretical framework for the current model is detailed in §3.

2.4. Heat flux evaluation

Heat flux at the wall cannot be directly retrieved from the infrared camera; therefore, a numerical simulation is performed based on the contact temperature measured by the camera. The Fourier heat diffusion equation is solved within the substrate as follows:

$$\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \mathbf{w} \cdot \nabla T = \alpha_w \nabla^2 T, \quad (2.3)$$

Figure 5: Contact temperature evolution (T_c) over time at different rotational speeds (n). The subfigures correspond to: (a) $n = 200$ r.p.m., (b) $n = 400$ r.p.m., (c) $n = 600$ r.p.m., and (d) $n = 800$ r.p.m., for a droplet diameter of $D = 2.45$ mm and an initial droplet temperature of $T_{d,0} = 0.5$ °C. The experimental data (red curve) is compared with the theoretical predictions of the current model (blue curve), with the shaded area indicating the measurement error of the experimental data.

where α_w is the thermal diffusivity of the substrate, and the velocity vector \mathbf{w} represents the substrate's motion, as the measurements are taken in the laboratory reference frame. Thermal properties are assumed to remain constant throughout the analysis.

The computational mesh is designed such that the top layer emulates the camera pixels, with each pixel assigned a velocity vector derived from moving calibration images. At the interface, a Dirichlet boundary condition is applied, where the temperature is specified using data from the infrared camera. Along the sides of the domain, zero-gradient boundary conditions are imposed. At the bottom, a zero-gradient condition is also applied. This choice is based on the consideration that the substrate is assumed to remain at room temperature, and the heat flux at the bottom is expected to be negligible.

The validity of the assumption is assessed by analysing the effect of the entrained air

within the boundary layer, which can lead to heating and a slight increase in temperature. To estimate this effect, the problem is treated analytically by solving a system of ordinary differential equations (ODEs) as described by [Millsaps & Pohlhausen \(1952\)](#), with the boundary condition modified to impose an adiabatic wall instead of a constant temperature. The details of the scaled temperature solution are provided in [Appendix A](#).

Under these conditions, the maximum expected temperature increase for the highest substrate speed is:

$$\Delta T_{\max} = \frac{(R\omega)^2}{c_{p,a}S(0)} + \frac{v_a\omega}{c_{p,a}}Q(0) \approx 0.2 \text{ [}^\circ\text{C]}, \quad (2.4)$$

where $S(0)$ and $Q(0)$ are reduced parameters evaluated at the wall based on the ODE solution.

Aside from the theoretical description, this statement is further supported by the experimental findings of [Cardone *et al.* \(1994\)](#). While the Nusselt number Nu reported in [Cardone *et al.* \(1994\)](#) could, in principle, be used to calculate the heat transfer coefficient h_{tc} for implementing a Robin-type boundary condition, the combination of a very small temperature difference and the uncertainty associated with the coefficient led us to adopt a zero-gradient boundary condition instead. Moreover, it is well established that for elliptic and parabolic equations, boundary effects diminish rapidly with increasing distance from the boundary ([Evans 2010](#)).

3. Heat transfer in a spreading drop, accounting for the thermal contact resistance

3.1. Problem formulation

The flow and temperature fields in the spreading droplet must satisfy the continuity, momentum, and energy equations ([Bird *et al.* 1966](#)). We assume incompressible flow, as the timescale and spatial region affected by compressibility are negligible in our experiments. This assumption has been thoroughly discussed and validated by [Weiss & Yarin \(1999\)](#). Under these conditions, the governing mass balance, momentum balance, and energy balance equations for the Newtonian flow \mathbf{v} , pressure p and temperature T are written as:

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0, \quad (3.1a)$$

$$\rho \frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + \rho(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} = -\nabla p + \mu \nabla^2 \mathbf{v}, \quad (3.1b)$$

$$\rho c_p \left(\frac{\partial T}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla T \right) = k \nabla^2 T. \quad (3.1c)$$

The decoupling of the thermal problem from the hydrodynamic one is a direct result of assuming constant thermo-physical properties. This simplifies the analysis, allowing the temperature field to be solved independently of the velocity and pressure fields.

Consider now the Cartesian coordinate system $\{x, y, z\}$ with the unit base vectors $\{\mathbf{e}_x, \mathbf{e}_y, \mathbf{e}_z\}$ with \mathbf{e}_z normal to the substrate interface directed toward the drop region. The velocity field in the fluid which accounts also for the viscous effects is defined as $\mathbf{v} = ue_x + ve_y + we_z$. The initial conditions and the boundary conditions far from the interface $z = 0$ are expressed as:

$$(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}_0) \times \mathbf{e}_z = 0, \quad T = T_{d,0} \quad \text{at } z \rightarrow \infty \forall t > 0 \text{ and at } t = 0 \forall z > 0, \quad (3.2a)$$

$$\mathbf{v} = 0, \quad T = T_{w,0} \quad \text{at } z \rightarrow -\infty \forall t > 0 \text{ and at } t = 0 \forall z < 0, \quad (3.2b)$$

where \mathbf{v}_0 is the velocity in the outer region of the drop far from the viscous boundary layer. The expression for the velocity \mathbf{v}_0 is obtained as the solution for the inviscid flow in the drop

Figure 6: Illustration of droplet impact on a rough substrate, highlighting the interface between the droplet and the substrate. The zoomed-in view emphasises the roughness of the substrate and the liquid-substrate contact area, with the white regions representing entrapped air. The red arrows in the zoomed area represent the heat flux, illustrating local variations where regions with better contact exhibit higher heat flux, while areas with entrapped air show reduced heat flux.

(Yarin & Weiss 1995; Roisman 2010). Here, $T_{d,0}$ and $T_{w,0}$ denote the initial temperatures of the droplet and the substrate, respectively.

The no-slip and zero-flux boundary conditions yield the following boundary conditions for the flow at the interface

$$\boldsymbol{v} = 0 \quad \text{at} \quad z = 0. \quad (3.3)$$

In this study, the temperature discontinuity arising from the presence of contact resistance between the substrate and the spreading droplet is taken into account. The physical meaning of this thermal resistance is illustrated in figure 6. The thermal effects are influenced by the morphology of the substrate and air entrapment at the interface. The region in the substrate and in the drop, associated with the thermal resistance, is characterized by an effective thickness h_R and effective heat conductivity k_R . If the value of h_R is much smaller than the thickness of the thermal boundary layer, the terms associated with the amount of heat added to the interface resistance layer can be neglected, and the heat flux q through the interface can thus be assumed continuous. On the other hand, this heat flux can be estimated in the form $q \approx k_R(T_d - T_w)/h_R$, where $h_R/k_R \equiv R_c$ is the thermal contact resistance.

The thermal boundary conditions at the interface are expressed as:

$$q = k_w \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right|_{\text{wall}} = k_d \left. \frac{\partial T}{\partial z} \right|_{\text{drop}}, \quad T_d - T_w = qR_c, \quad \text{at} \quad z = 0. \quad (3.4)$$

This modified boundary condition reflects the physical reality of many practical systems, where contact resistance cannot be neglected, and highlights a key distinction from prior studies that assume perfect thermal continuity at the interface.

3.2. Viscous flow in the drop region

The similarity solution for the flow in the lamella in the Cartesian coordinate system $\{x, y, z\}$, fixed at the substrate surface, has been obtained in Roisman (2009, 2010)

$$\boldsymbol{v} = f(\xi) \frac{(x + U_x t) \boldsymbol{e}_x + y \boldsymbol{e}_y}{t} - 2 \sqrt{\frac{y}{t}} g(\xi) \boldsymbol{e}_z, \quad \xi \equiv \frac{z}{\sqrt{vt}}, \quad (3.5)$$

(a) The scaled vertical velocity component $g(\xi)$ as a function of ξ .

(b) The scaled in-plane velocity component $f(\xi)$ (in the x - y plane) as a function of ξ .

Figure 7: Numerical solutions for the scaled velocity components as functions of the similarity variable ξ . Panel (a) shows the scaled vertical velocity $g(\xi)$, while panel (b) presents the scaled in-plane velocity $f(\xi)$, representing the velocity components in the x - y plane. These results are derived from the coupled ordinary differential equations described in equations (3.7).

where ξ is the similarity variable. At large values of ξ this field approaches the outer inviscid flow in the spreading drop. The outer solution (Yarin & Weiss 1995; Roisman 2010), which satisfies exactly the mass and momentum balance equations is

$$\mathbf{v}_0 = \frac{(x + U_x \tau) \mathbf{e}_x + y \mathbf{e}_y - 2z \mathbf{e}_z}{t}, \quad (3.6)$$

where U_x is the tangential, x -component of the impact velocity relative to the substrate.

Substituting the expression (3.5) in the mass and momentum balance equations (3.1a) and (3.1b) yields the following system of the ordinary differential equations

$$f = g', \quad (3.7a)$$

$$f'' + \frac{f'}{2}(\xi + 4g) + f = f^2, \quad (3.7b)$$

which can be solved computationally, subject to the no-penetrability conditions and the no-slip conditions at the wall and continuity of the velocity in the outer region

$$f = 1, \quad \text{as } \xi \rightarrow \infty, \quad (3.8a)$$

$$g' = g = 0, \quad \text{as } \xi \rightarrow 0. \quad (3.8b)$$

For completeness the functions $g(\xi)$ and $f(\xi)$ first reported in Roisman (2010) are plotted in figure 7.

3.3. Heat transfer in the drop and substrate at high Prandtl numbers $Pr \gg 1$

The solution for the temperature fields in the spreading drop at $z \geq 0$ and the solid substrate $z \leq 0$, accounting for the contact resistance is assumed in the form associated with the known solution for heat conduction (Carslaw & Jaeger 1959)

$$T_d = T_{c0} + (T_{d0} - T_{c0}) \left[c_d \exp\left(\frac{t}{t_R} + 2\zeta_d \sqrt{\frac{t}{t_R}}\right) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{t}{t_R}} + \zeta_d\right) + \theta(\zeta_d) \right], \quad (3.9a)$$

$$T_w = T_{c0} + (T_{w0} - T_{c0}) \left[\exp\left(\frac{t}{t_R} - 2\zeta_w \sqrt{\frac{t}{t_R}}\right) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{t}{t_R}} - \zeta_w\right) - \operatorname{erf}(\zeta_w) \right], \quad (3.9b)$$

$$\zeta_d \equiv \frac{z}{2\sqrt{\alpha_d t}}, \quad \zeta_w \equiv \frac{z}{2\sqrt{\alpha_w t}} \quad (3.9c)$$

where c_d and T_{c0} are constants and t_R is a characteristic time associated with the duration of the propagation of the thermal boundary layer inside the contact region of thickness h_R . These constants will be determined from the boundary conditions.

Expressions (3.9a)–(3.9b) satisfy the heat conduction equation in the wall. However, the form (3.9a) yields only an approximate solution for the temperature field in the drop if the convective terms are smaller than the conductive terms. In the case of a large Prandtl number, the thickness of the thermal boundary layer is much smaller than that of the viscous boundary layer. In this case, since both the value of the normal velocity and its gradient at the wall are equal to zero, the convection effects are indeed small. Moreover, the experiments are usually considered at times $t \gg t_R$. The asymptotic expression for the gradient of the drop temperature taking into account a small value of t_R/t is obtained from (3.9a) in the form

$$\frac{\partial T_d}{\partial z} \approx \frac{(T_{d0} - T_{c0})}{2\sqrt{\alpha_d t}} \left[\exp(-\zeta_d^2) \theta'(0) + \theta'(\zeta) \right], \quad \text{if } t \gg t_R. \quad (3.10)$$

This approximate expression can be used for the estimation of the small convective terms in the energy equation if the Prandtl number is large.

Substitution of expressions (3.9) and (3.10) in the energy equation (3.1c) yields the following similarity equation

$$\theta''(\zeta_d) + 2\zeta_d \theta'(\zeta_d) + 4Pr_d^{1/2} g \left[\frac{\zeta_d}{Pr_d^{1/2}} \right] \left\{ \theta'(\zeta_d) + \exp(-\zeta_d^2) \theta'(0) \right\} = 0, \quad (3.11)$$

where the Prandtl number is defined as $Pr_d \equiv \sqrt{\nu/\alpha_d}$ and the dimensionless function g is determined from the similarity solution for the drop velocity field.

This ordinary differential equation has to be solved subject to the boundary conditions

$$\theta = 0, \quad \text{at } \zeta_d = 0 \quad (3.12a)$$

$$\theta \rightarrow 1, \quad \text{as } \zeta_d \rightarrow \infty. \quad (3.12b)$$

In figure 8, the theoretical predictions for the dimensionless function $\theta(\zeta_d)$ are shown for various Prandtl numbers. The computed values of $\theta'(0)$ as a function of Pr_d are shown in figure 9. The value of the constants T_{c0} and t_R are determined from the boundary conditions (3.4) associated with the thermal contact resistance

$$T_{c0} = \frac{e_w T_{w0} + e_d c_d T_{d0}}{e_w + e_d c_d}, \quad t_R = \left(\frac{e_d e_w}{e_d + e_w} R_c \right)^2, \quad c_d = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \theta'(0)}{2}. \quad (3.13)$$

where $\theta(\zeta_d)$ is a dimensionless function given in (3.9a), e_d and e_w are the thermal effusivities of the drop and substrate materials, respectively. Finally, the substrate temperature at the

Figure 8: Theoretically predicted values of $\theta(\zeta_d)$ at various values of the Prandtl number.

Figure 9: Theoretically predicted values of $\theta'(0)$ and c_d as a function of the Prandtl number.

interface $z = 0$ and the heat flux are obtained using (3.9) in the form

$$T_{w,\text{interface}} = T_{c0} + (T_{w0} - T_{c0}) \exp\left(\frac{t}{t_R}\right) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{t}{t_R}}\right), \quad (3.14a)$$

$$q_{\text{interface}} = \frac{T_{d0} - T_{w0}}{\sqrt{t_R}} \frac{e_w e_d \sqrt{\pi} \theta'(0)}{2e_w + e_d \sqrt{\pi} \theta'(0)} \exp\left(\frac{t}{t_R}\right) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{t}{t_R}}\right) \quad (3.14b)$$

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 10: Comparison of experimental contact temperatures with theoretical predictions for various models. (a) Seki *et al.* (1978) (b) Roisman (2010) (c) The current model. Each plot includes experimental data (circles), a perfect agreement line (black dashed), and experimental error bounds (red dashed).

Figure 11: Heat transfer coefficient, h_{tc} , as a function of time, t , for different rotational speeds and droplet diameters. Experimental data (solid lines) are compared with theoretical predictions (dashed lines). Figures (a) and (b) correspond to substrate rotational speeds of 200 and 800 r.p.m., respectively. Shaded regions indicate measurement uncertainty.

The value of the thermal contact resistance, R_c , required to determine the characteristic time scale t_R was obtained by performing a best fit to each experimental dataset and subsequently averaging the results. The mean value was found to be $2.39 \times 10^{-5} \text{ m}^2\text{K}/\text{W}$ with a 95% confidence interval of $[1.73 \times 10^{-5}, 3.65 \times 10^{-5}] \text{ m}^2\text{K}/\text{W}$.

A comparison between the experimental results and the three models can be seen below in figures (10a)-(10c). The model of [Seki *et al.* \(1978\)](#) has a rather fair agreement as shown in figure (10c), which can be explained by the fact that for our investigated Pr_d , the convective effects are small and the understimation of the contact temperature is balanced by the missing contact resistance condition. On the other hand, the model of [Roisman \(2010\)](#) consistently underestimates the contact temperature due to the missing contact resistance term. The present model incorporates both heat convection and contact resistance, resulting in a very good agreement with the experimental data.

The heat transfer coefficient at the interface is readily derived by scaling the heat flux to the initial temperature difference between the substrate and the spreading drop as:

$$h_{tc} = \frac{q}{\Delta T} = \frac{e_w e_d \sqrt{\pi} \theta'(0)}{\sqrt{t_R} (2e_w + e_d \sqrt{\pi} \theta'(0))} \exp\left(\frac{t}{t_R}\right) \operatorname{erfc}\left(\sqrt{\frac{t}{t_R}}\right), \quad (3.15)$$

This quantity is plotted in figures 11a and 11b for the two extreme substrate velocities tested (≈ 200 and 800 r.p.m.), each at varying droplet diameters. Intermediate velocities were also investigated and exhibited qualitatively similar trends; they are therefore omitted here for conciseness. As expected, neither the droplet diameter nor the substrate velocity significantly affects the heat flux. This is consistent with the theoretical model predictions. The results demonstrate good agreement between experimental data (solid lines) and theoretical predictions (dashed lines), as shown in figure 11, where shaded regions represent measurement uncertainty. Notably, the inclusion of the contact resistance boundary condition results in a finite heat flux at $t = 0$, in contrast with the singularity predicted by the models of Seki *et al.* (1978) and Roisman (2010). This finite behaviour highlights the importance of incorporating realistic boundary conditions in heat transfer models to accurately capture interfacial dynamics during droplet impact.

4. Conclusion

A theoretical and experimental study was conducted to capture the heat flux that occurs when a liquid drop spreads over a moving solid surface. The analytical framework extends the self-similar spreading solution of Roisman (2010) by introducing a finite thermal-contact resistance at the substrate interface. This modification serves to eliminate the singularity that was predicted by earlier models that neglected contact resistance. The consequence of accounting for contact resistance, of closed-form expressions for the interfacial temperature and heat flux, could be achieved. The transient contact temperature during impact was measured using time-resolved infrared thermography. For each test condition investigated, the revised model reproduces the measured temperature and the wall heat flux to within the experimental measurement uncertainty. Within the explored ranges of droplet size, substrate speed and thermal boundary conditions, neither droplet diameter nor substrate velocity exerts a measurable influence on the subsequent thermal evolution. In particular, while the substrate motion induces shear within the liquid, the associated viscous dissipation remains too weak at the investigated velocities to alter the temperature field within the drop significantly. As a result, the dominant mechanism governing interfacial heat transfer remains conduction and convection across the liquid–solid interface.

Supplementary data. Supplementary material and movies are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15720949>

Acknowledgements. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation program under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101072551 (TRACES). This work is partially supported by the joint DFG/FWF Collaborative Research Centre CREATOR (DFG: Project-ID 492661287/TRR 361; FWF: 10.55776/F90) at TU Darmstadt, TU Graz and JKU Linz.

Declaration of interests. The authors report no conflict of interest.

Appendix A. Airflow past a rotating disk

For the sake of clarity, we report here the solution of the 3D boundary layer problem of air due to a rotating disk. For the derivation of the equations, the interested reader is referred to Kármán (1921) and Millsaps & Pohlhausen (1952). A dimensionless system of ordinary differential equations can be found by imposing:

$$u_r = rf(z), \quad u_\theta = rg(z), \quad u_z = h(z), \quad p = p(z). \quad (\text{A } 1)$$

For the thermal distribution:

$$t = r^2s(z) + q(z) + t_\infty. \quad (\text{A } 2)$$

Figure 12: Solutions to the 3D boundary layer problem for a rotating disk. (a) Hydrodynamic components $H(\xi)$, $F(\xi)$, and $G(\xi)$ represent non-dimensional vertical, radial, and azimuthal velocities, respectively. (b) Thermodynamic components $S(\xi)$ and $Q(\xi)$.

The non-dimensional incompressible Navier-Stokes equations simplify to the following system:

$$F^2 - G^2 + HF' = F'', \quad (\text{A } 3)$$

$$2FG + HG = G'', \quad (\text{A } 4)$$

$$HH' + 2F' = P', \quad (\text{A } 5)$$

$$2F + H' = 0. \quad (\text{A } 6)$$

Where:

$$f = \omega F, \quad g = \omega G, \quad h = (\nu\omega)^{1/2}H, \quad p = \rho\nu\omega P, \quad z = \left(\frac{\nu}{\omega}\right)^{1/2} \zeta. \quad (\text{A } 7)$$

Subject to the following boundary conditions:

$$F(0) = 0, \quad G(0) = 1, \quad H(0) = 0, \quad F(\infty) = 0, \quad G(\infty) = 0. \quad (\text{A } 8)$$

The corresponding energy equation reduces to:

$$\text{Pr}_a HS' - \text{Pr}_a H'S - \text{Pr}_a (F'^2 + G'^2) = S'', \quad (\text{A } 9)$$

$$\text{Pr}_a HQ' - (4S + 12\text{Pr}_a F^2) = Q''. \quad (\text{A } 10)$$

Here, Pr_a represents the Prandtl number of air.

The first set of four ODEs, given in equations (A 3)–(A 6), describes the hydrodynamic part of the problem, as proposed by Kármán (1921) and solved numerically by Cochran (1934). The solution to these equations is shown in figure 12(a), which presents the non-dimensional vertical, radial, and azimuthal velocity components $H(\xi)$, $F(\xi)$, and $G(\xi)$, respectively. The second set of equations, equations (A 9)–(A 10), governs the thermodynamic problem. The solution, displayed in figure 12(b), represents the non-dimensional temperature distribution $S(\xi)$ and $Q(\xi)$.

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